

Analysis the quality of life for the citizens in the level of the Zabol city.

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Abstract

Today the quality of urban life is the key concept in urban planning .on this basis in many countries the planners are trying to show the different geographical levels so that they enable identify optimal solutions to improve lives of disadvantages areas according to studied indices. The goal of this research is analyzing the quality life of citizens in city of Zabol. In present study, the quality of life have been considered as an interaction among sources, possibilities and provided opportunities for supplying human needs and also receive, assessment and satisfactory of individuals and groups for meeting their needs in a specific location .the research method is descriptive – analytic and is based on documentary librarian, field studies. To achieve this goal we set out to investigate and gather information and questionnaires were distributed in city of Zabol and have been analyzed by using Vicor model. The result assessment and ranking of different districts of Zabol according to seven indices of quality of life using VIKOR model have been studied and shows that district 3 is in first place and district 4 is in fifth place.

Key words: Quality of life, Sustainable development, District, Zabol

Introduction

Quality of life in terms of a wide range of fields, including the fields of international development, healthcare, and politics is being used. Quality of life should not be a standard of living that is based largely on income, confused. Instead, standard indicators Quality of life include not only wealth and employment, but also include environmental, physical and mental health, education, recreation and leisure, and social belonging, too.

Discussion of the quality of life and sustainable development released today in literature to plan for social development and the new economy topics raised and has special status and national and local-level Governments and many institutions on its index and measurement of work (Kharazmi, 2008). In the new issue of sustainable human development is a major emphasis on the important issues of the policy-based allocation of resources more efficient, which is a major issue of social justice is Possible (Marsoosi, 2004: 25). Consequently, during the most recent decades, policy makers, social welfare and improve their living standards Persisted (Jabbari, 2002: 55).

With the beginning of the 1980s, a common attitude with titles Index of Sustainable Economic Welfare (ISEW) and Physical Quality of life Index (PQLI) were raised (Henderson and et al, 2000). Quality of life assessment of infant mortality, literacy and life expectancy as criteria for assessment of welfare and well-being, opinions (Ekins and Max, 1992).

Today, most of the urban quality of life as a key concept in urban planning. On this basis in many developed countries, planners are trying to show the levels of quality of life in the different geographical levels are optimal solutions can be used in this way to improve the quality of life of backward regions and they examined. One of the major concerns of every General Manager in the professional decision making activities for achieving, maintaining and improving productivity, which is the most important topics of interest to the Organization (Azar & Azim, 2002) and is one of the principles of decision making for managers, performance evaluation, which shall be in the form of being scientific has an effective decisions help (Mirghafori & Shafiei, 2007).

Due to the holistic approach lies in the quality of life issues, analysis and evaluation in developing countries, and the main role in the holistic planning. Iran, which is a development of the people in connection with the geographical formation, forming the shape of a model is the severity of spatial development was commenced. (Faraji, 2010: 3).

The goal of research

- ✓ Identify and depict the cultural, social and economic life condition of the citizens, accurately.
- ✓ Recognition and classification of quality of life indicators.
- ✓ Identifying the most important and issues for future actions to improve the quality of life in the city of Zabol.
- ✓ Date base creation of variants and underlying components affecting quality of life

Theoretical fundamentals and history of research:

Quality of life is a broad concept that ideas like, life, life is precious, life is satisfying and happy life in the (McCrea and et al, 2006). David Smith was the first geographer about quality of life, prosperity and social justice, he spoke in geography. Smith emphasized that indicators of health, housing, public services, happiness, family, education, employment opportunities, salaries and wages, food, franchise, life expectancy, per capita consumption of animal protein, the percentage of school enrollment, number of phone mean newspapers and the like form (Smith, 2002: 160-169).

Domain-connected quality of life may be at any time as the date has been extended. Economists, social scientists and government of each particular viewpoint to look at this issue (Baldwin & Godfry & Propper, 1992: 1). This stems from the fact that a range of indicators relating to the quality of life in the fall. Feeding and clothing ranging from health care, social environment and physical environment surrounding include (Drewnevski, 2005: 53-70). Although some of the sources of living, quality of life is translated.

FO, Quality of life is defined as: "the quality of life in many cases the two sets of objective and subjective parameters is studied.

Indicators of subjective perceptions of the assessment, evaluation and satisfaction of citizens in urban environment received, whereas objective indicators connected to observable facts. According to the definition of, Focal be said that quality of life can be classified in various ways and studied. One of these categories connected to the research work(Zapf, 1984) and (Craglia et al, 2004) where it is stated that, if the individual subjective feelings and objective conditions are favorable living environment, as having or happiness is defined. And an assessment of the environmental conditions and the individual is bad, as it is deprived remembered.

If a person's subjective evaluation was good, but the objective conditions are bad, the process is said to be compatible if the same person's mental condition favorable objective conditions of their environment, is bad, this mismatch is introduced. Several methods for measuring quality of life in urban environments have been used. For example, (Moro et al, 2008) and (Das, 2008) have proposed methods by which these methods could make Quality of life in the context of selected features or aspects of life should be assessed.

(Repheal et al, 1997) quality of life so that one of the important features of life enjoyed define. While the RIVM group claims that quality of life is immaterial equipment life issues, with the objective of such person in accordance with the perceptions about health, living conditions, work, family, and has been determined (RIVM, 2000). Perhaps the concept of quality of life and quality of life conceptual drawing for the four basic dimensions of human life, namely economic, environmental aspects, social aspects, and finally cultural dimensions - political adapted to provide a standard level of expectations (Faraji molaei, 2010). In other words, quality of life is a multidimensional concept that requires a firsthand analysis of expectations and satisfaction of citizens (Faraji molaei, 2010).

Study areas and various cities in the United States in terms of quality of life showed significant differences in some indicators show the different regions (Hagget, 2000: 458-460). On the other hand there is a significant connection between quality of life indicators. In Helsinki, research has shown the quality of life and social maladaptive behaviors such as suicide, social deviance, Alcoholism and there is a direct connection between divorces. While the quality of their housing situation is a reflection of the socio - economic (Shakoie, 2001).

In American Ghettoes race, early mortality, influenza, heart disease and a major cause of death in black men is murder. Non- standard housing in Harlem ghetto 50 percent unemployment rate for 25 to 30 percent, with almost half the young men are not able to find work. As a result, residents of these areas are under severe economic pressure and psychological (Shakoie, 1990: 79-80). Thus, the concept of quality of life is associated largely with the concept of welfare. Although there is no consensus on welfare, but welfare is a concept that describes the welfare, security of life and poverty alleviation and therefore closely connected concepts such as justice is (Barry, 2001: 6-12).

Research method

The research method is descriptive – analytic and is based on documentary librarian, field studies. To achieve this goal we set out to investigate and gather information and questionnaires were distributed in city of Zabol and have been analyzed by using Vicor model.

Area of study

Zabol is located the geographical coordinates 31 degrees north latitude and 61 degrees and 2 minutes and 39 minutes east. The extent of Zabol is 2084 hectares, which is equal to 0.13 percent of the area encompasses the city. Zabol in term of land distance is 210 km from Zahedan city in southeastern, 1538 km north of Tehran, 366 km North West of Birjand and 834 km from Mashhad and thus be associated with the centers of neighboring provinces and other parts.

Figure (1): Map of Zabol, Source: research findings

Discussion and conclusion

Evaluation and ranking of the seven areas of Zabol on quality of life indicators using of VIKOR model.

The dominant approach used in this study, areas of Zabol rating based on seven indicators of quality of life are examined. In this research, the areas of Zabol are being rated based on quality measures (table number 1)

Table (1): The indicators used to measure areas of Zabol Ranking based on the quality of life

indicator
Good governance and freedom of expression
Environmental conditions
Education
Social Communications
Health
Individual activity
Security

Source: search results

Due to the characteristics of the study area some indicators for measuring quality of life based on the ranking of Zabol areas have been considered in this section, each of the areas of Zabol based on different measures are been evaluated. The advantage of this model is that the assessment of measures does not require the expertise but raw data can be used. However, because such measures are not as raw data, they were analyzed by experts from 1 to 10.

Process of models and research findings

Following this research we investigate, how to implement the model process, is fully explained and how to use it in the context of the case study is discussed.

First phase

Determine the measures

In this section each areas of Zabol, based on measures and indicators are evaluated. Because these measures and indicators are in form of raw data, they were analyzed by experts from 1 to 10(Table number 2).

Table (2): Conversion of qualitative indicators to slightly

0	1	2	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Very low		low		average		much		very much	

Source: search results

Table (3): Results criteria and indicators

indicator districts	Good governance and freedom of expression	Environmental conditions	Education	Social Communications	Health	Individual activity	Security
aij	0.180	0.200	0.150	0.190	0.210	0.185	0.185
District 1	4	4	5	7	5	5	4
District 2	5	5	7	8	7	6	5
District 3	5	5	8	8	8	6	7
District 4	3	3	3	6	3	5	3
District 5	4	5	6	7	5	6	7

Source: search results

Second phase

Normalized decision matrix can be performed by the following formula

$$r_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}}$$

First, all amounts of matrix raised to the power of 2 and the total sum of each column is pluralized Then the square root of the sum of each column and each of the values obtained by dividing the square root.

Table (4): the sum of each column

indicator districts	Good governance and freedom of expression	Environmental conditions	Education	Social Communications	Health	Individual activity	Security
aij	0.180	0.200	0.150	0.190	0.210	0.185	0.185
District 1	4	4	5	7	5	5	4
District 2	5	5	7	8	7	6	5
District 3	5	5	8	8	8	6	7
District 4	3	3	3	6	3	5	3
District 5	4	5	6	7	5	6	7
Total	21	21	29	36	28	28	26

Source: search results

Table (5): Continue Table 4

indicator districts	Good governance and freedom of expression	Environmental conditions	Education	Social Communications	Health	Individual activity	Security
aij	0.180	0.200	0.150	0.190	0.210	0.185	0.185
aij	16	16	25	49	25	25	16
District 1	25	25	49	64	49	36	25
District 2	25	25	64	64	64	36	49
District 3	9	9	9	36	9	25	9
District 4	16	25	36	49	25	36	49
Total	81	100	183	262	172	158	148

Source: search results

Table (6) divided by the square root of the sum of each column and each of the values of the square root of the sum

indicator districts	Good governance and freedom of expression	Environmental conditions	Education	Social Communications	Health	Individual activity	Security
aij	0.180	0.200	0.150	0.190	0.210	0.185	0.185
District 1	0.44	0.4	0.36	0.43	0.38	0.40	0.32
District 2	0.55	0.5	0.51	0.49	0.53	0.48	0.41
District 3	0.55	0.5	0.59	0.49	0.61	0.48	0.56
District 4	1	0.3	0.22	0.37	0.23	0.40	0.25
District 5	0.44	0.5	0.44	0.49	0.53	0.48	0.56

Source: search results

Third phase

Weighting of the normal matrix

For weighting of the normal matrix, values of normal matrix for each of the options multiply on the weight of measures (This was previously obtained from other methods). (Table 7).

Table (7): The weight of the normal matrix

indicator districts	Good governance and freedom of expression	Environmental conditions	Education	Social Communications	Health	Individual activity	Security
ajj	0.180	0.200	0.150	0.190	0.210	0.185	0.185
District 1	0.079	0.08	0.054	0.081	0.079	0.074	0.060
District 2	0.099	1	0.076	0.093	0.111	0.084	0.075
District 3	0.099	1	0.088	0.093	0.129	0.084	0.103
District 4	0.018	0.06	0.033	0.070	0.043	0.074	0.046
District 5	0.079	1	0.066	0.093	0.111	0.084	0.103

Source: search results

Fourth phase

Determining the amount of the highest and lowest values of normal weight matrix. (Table 8)

Here, the greatest number is that has the greatest positive value, and the smallest is the number that has the most negative value.

So if our measure is negative, the largest number will be in reverse, i.e. the lowest, and the smallest number will be the highest value and vice versa.

$$f_i^* = \max_j f_{ij}; \quad f_i^- = \min_j f_{ij}$$

Table (8): Determine the values of the highest and lowest values of normal weight matrix

f max	0.099	0.1	0.88	0.093	0.129	0.084	0.103
f min	0.018	0.06	0.033	0.070	0.043	0.074	0.046
f+ - F-	0.072	0.94	0.055	0.023	0.086	0.01	0.057

Source: search results

Step Five:

The desirability determine the index (S) and dissatisfaction index (R):

$$S_j = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot \frac{f_i^* - f_{ij}}{f_i^* - f_i^-}; \quad R_j = \max_i \left[w_i \cdot \frac{f_i^* - f_{ij}}{f_i^* - f_i^-} \right]$$

*= the largest number of normal weight matrix for each column

fij = Item number for each measure in normal weight matrix

f-= smallest number of normal matrix for each column

Naturally, the options for each measure, a utility index is obtained that the sum of them specifies the final index of Sj.

The greatest Sj of each option for each measure, is dissatisfaction index (R) of that option.(table 9)

Security	Good governance and freedom of expression	Environmental conditions	Education	Social Communications	Health	Individual activity	Security	S	R
ajj	0.180	0.200	0.150	0.190	0.210	0.185	0.185		
District 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
District 2	0	0	0.218	0	0.209	0	0.492	0.919	0.492
District 3	0.246	0.92	0.618	0.521	0.581	0.111	0.754	0.3751	0.757
District 4	1	1	1	1	1	0.111	1	6.111	1
District 5	0.246	0	0.4	0	0.209	0	0	0.855	0.246

Table (9): The desirability determine the index (S) and dissatisfaction index (R)

Source: search results

Step Six:

Final ranking calculate Q and options through the following formula:

$$Q_j = v \cdot \frac{S_j - S^-}{S^* - S^-} + (1 - v) \cdot \frac{R_j - R^-}{R^* - R^-}$$

The maximum value of Q as the best option is selected (Table 10).

Table (10): Final ranking model

Rank	Districts	Score
3	District 1	1
2	District 2	1.45
1	District 3	4.53
5	District 4	0.000
4	District 5	0.68

Source: search results

The results of the evaluation and ranking of regions with respect to the parameters of the study show that the District 3 in the first place, District 1 in third place, District 5 in fourth place and finally District 4 is in fifth place.

Conclusions

Quality of life of a community development strategy that includes the most important factors that determine the living conditions in the community and personal welfare are.

Quality of life is the most basic issues of political and economic sciences. Where the material parameters of economic development and domestic production along with other material parameters such as

Quality of work, level of education, culture, medicine and health standards, quality leisure, environment, political environment, individual happiness and liberty and national unity are examined. Accordingly, in many developed countries, planners are trying to show the quality of life in different geographical levels. In order to obtain an optimal strategy to improve the quality of life indicators assessed in terms of backward areas pedigree.

Enjoyment of residents of a city, Clean water, electricity, telephone services, public transport (including bus and subway fleet), Low density traffic areas, appropriate services such as restaurants, theaters, cinemas, sports halls, Adequate green space, parks, forests, cities, schools and universities with high standards of teaching and ... In the meantime, health, environment and safety connected quality of life in cities is a priority. There are also hospitals and health services tailored to the relative population of each city, a city of quality indicators. Benefit residents of suitable and affordable housing, and services available to them and... well, another indicator of is an ideal city.

In present study, the quality of life have been considered as an interaction among sources, possibilities and provided opportunities for supplying human needs and also receive, assessment and satisfactory of individuals and groups for meeting their needs in a specific location .the research method is descriptive – analytic and is based on documentary librarian, field studies. To achieve this goal we set out to investigate and gather information and questionnaires were distributed in city of Zabol and have been analyzed by using Vicor model. The result assessment and ranking of different districts of Zabol according to seven indices of quality of life using VIKOR model have been studied and shows that district 3 is in first place and district 4 is in fifth place.

Suggestion

Meet the basic needs of the people of the city of Zabol ideally

Economic, social and politic empowerment of people of the city of Zabol.

Increasing social capital and trust of citizens.

Social development opportunities in order to develop public institutions.

Increasing the choice of people

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